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A collection of articles by Asian scholars
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**PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL DIRECTIONS OF PREPARING
FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL
ACTIVITIES AIMING AT SOCIALIZATION OF STUDENTS BASED ON A
GENDER APPROACH**

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Abstract: This article comprehensively analyzes the pedagogical and psychological aspects of the process of preparing future teachers for professional and pedagogical activities aimed at socializing students based on a gender approach. The importance of the gender approach in the personal development of students, social behavior and understanding of social roles is highlighted. The psychological preparation factors for future teachers to form gender sensitivity, overcome stereotypes, establish dialogue and education on the basis of equality are substantiated. The article also extensively discusses the role of psychopedagogical competencies, a person-centered approach, empathy and communicative skills in the process of gender socialization.

Keywords: gender approach, socialization, professional and pedagogical training, psychological competence, communicative skills, gender equality, social role, student personality.

Introduction.

Today, the humanitarian paradigm, which is gaining increasing popularity in education, is the basis for establishing relationships based on diversity, diversity, mutual respect, the uniqueness of the inner world of the individual, and creating favorable opportunities for self-development, regardless of gender. When approached from a gender perspective, gender competence is part of the personal qualities of a future teacher. Gender competence allows for the emergence and manifestation of gender ethics, preventing gender inequality, leadership in communication, addressing the student's inner world, being able to communicate with students of different genders, establishing relationships based on mutual trust, and improving the psychological environment.

The theory of a modern gender approach also serves as a methodological basis for gender pedagogy. To date, the attention of philosophers, psychologists, and educators to gender competence has increased. Because the study of the pedagogical directions of the gender approach is of particular importance from the point of view

of gender socialization of individual students. The formation of gender competence in the process of higher pedagogical education requires a specific methodological toolkit. The processes of globalization in society have a positive and negative impact on gender relations and gender communication situations. Since the gender approach is a new approach for pedagogical science, the need to study positive and negative situations in the process of gender relations is more urgent than ever.

The gender strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at providing equal education for students of both sexes and opportunities to enter into successful gender relations. Special attention is paid to creating a pedagogical environment that serves to develop a culture of gender dialogue, gender cooperation, and gender-specific dialogical relations in the educational process. The gender approach and gender strategies used in the Uzbek education system are unique, in which priority is given to national mentality, historical and cultural traditions, and values. The opportunities for socialization of boys and girls are expanded based on the formation of gender roles that are characteristic of each of them.

It is an indisputable fact that gender communication is of great importance in the pedagogical activity of future teachers aimed at gender socialization of students. Because communication has its own gender function. This function is carried out based on a gender approach. This function takes a leading place in the gender socialization system and ensures the integration of all other competencies. This competency is formed in pedagogical processes outside the classroom and outside the classroom. In the process of pedagogical practice and work on the “4 + 2” model, students directly communicate with students. In this process, they choose a communication style that is specific to each of them, based on the gender affiliation of students. Within the cognitive function of gender communication, gender competence acquires a new meaning and manifests itself in the process of developing cognitive abilities in future teachers, thinking about their own gender characteristics and gender identity, the formation of masculine and feminine individuality, acquiring professional competence to take into account the gender characteristics of their students, and mastering teaching and professional activities.

In the process of professional training of future teachers, it is of particular importance to familiarize students with the psychophysiological gender characteristics. In this case, boys and girls have different speech patterns, perception, imagination, attention, memory, speech, and different voice timbres. At the same time, future teachers are required to be well aware of the developmental patterns that are characteristic of each of them. Therefore, it is important to determine the characteristic aspects of the gender competence of a future teacher. The main function of gender competence is to determine the position and point of view of future teachers

in the context of their valuable activities. Because these are part of the personal qualities of a future teacher. The valuable function of gender competence is to present valuable cultural values inherent in the Uzbek people to future teachers, and to direct them to master national and universal values. A person, including a future teacher, who has not mastered values, will not be able to effectively function in a micro-society and communicate with its members. If students do not have professional and personal values, they will not have the competence to distinguish which values are important for Uzbek society. The value function of gender competence ensures that the perceptual communication with students is based on emotional experiences. Therefore, future teachers should have the opportunity to exert emotional influence in the process of communication with students. Only then will the teacher's communication with students be effective. In most cases, pedagogical communication, which takes on an emotional character, and sometimes does not have such a character, can hinder the dialogue between the teacher and students. In this situation, future teachers are required to study the psychological and emotional aspects of the subjects of the communication process and to know the requirements for communication situations.

The communication between a teacher and a student should have a valuable content and essence, be carried out on the basis of mutual respect, attention, trust, and understanding. Analysis of pedagogical situations shows that today it is extremely difficult for teachers and students to understand each other. As a result, various unpleasant situations arise. Today, teacher-student relations are taking on a valuable direction.

In the formation of the gender competence of a future teacher, special attention should be paid to the factor of his awareness of socio-cultural knowledge. The roles played by boys, approached from the perspective of gender, differ in their uniqueness from the roles played by girls. Existing stereotypical ideas about the male gender form empathy in male teachers. As a result, students of this gender expect such qualities as empathy, attention, care, emotional support from them. Thus, the stereotypes that exist in society, which are now outdated, are eliminated, and a new valuable model of interpersonal relationships is introduced.

The socio-cultural roles inherent in boys and girls are an integral part of the culture and mentality of the Uzbek people. Boys and girls, who are representatives of a particular nationality, acquire their own roles, forms of manifestation of emotions, experiences, and, in turn, present them to the younger generation. In the formation of gender competence in future teachers, it is important to equip students with knowledge of a socio-cultural nature. It is of particular pedagogical importance for future teachers to master methods of supporting students in the process of socializing

them.

The fact that today's students are very quickly exposed to the influence of "popular culture", their insufficiently formed sense of gender identity, disregard for gender roles, high-spiritedness, and the need to start socializing students very early on based on a gender-neutral approach. Future teachers should be aware that gender norms are changing in modern Uzbek society, and new norms are replacing them.

In the gender socialization of students, it is of particular pedagogical importance to be able to distinguish between the qualities inherent in girls and boys and to know which of them is dominant. Future teachers should pay attention to the fact that student-teacher relationships are not extrapolated and do not cause discomfort. Therefore, we have come to the conclusion that it is appropriate to provide students with knowledge of gender roles, gender culture, sociocultural knowledge, gender cultural studies, and gender relations in the process of higher pedagogical education. Because this knowledge creates a favorable opportunity for students to demonstrate their capabilities, enter into productive communication, and establish valuable relationships with each other.

The reflexive function of gender competence is a method of activity consisting in reflecting on the actions, motives, and consequences of boys and girls, who are the subjects of the communication process. The mechanism of students' reflexive activity is to acquire gender-related knowledge, manage the process of gender relations, and create a favorable environment for gender self-awareness. The reflexive component of gender competence is to listen to each other, communicate, encourage boys and girls to support their dialogue, and is expressed in the specific characteristics of each gender. Future teachers should be able to substantiate their points of view with evidence, demonstrate their inclination towards equality, treat boys and girls with equal respect, be able to summarize the results of the collaborative process, and defend their points of view with a logical approach, enriching their experience in the field of gender socialization of students. Future teachers should master the experience of building constructive social relationships between boys and girls, and respectfully treat students' conclusions and judgments based on a situational approach. The inclinations, abilities of the subjects of the communication process serve as a guiding stimulus for the self-development and self-expression of representatives of both sexes.

The reflexive function of gender competence directs future teachers to enter into a constructive dialogue with students, to acquire knowledge and methods of activity that serve to ensure their socialization. Because each of the boys and girls has the opportunity to master their own values. At the same time, in the process of mastering these values, it is required to take into account the interests and interests of those

around them. Their constant support and encouragement of each other, their readiness to cooperate are an important condition for gender socialization.

One of the important conditions is the realization of the need to strengthen the relationship between boys and girls on the basis of a value-based approach. Then it will be easier to choose compromise methods in the process of their socialization. Never create a mood of competition and leadership between boys and girls. Being in such a mood leads to a deterioration of the atmosphere in the educational institution, and conflicts of various levels arise among students in the classroom. –

The gender function of gender competence also plays an important role in preparing future teachers for professional activity. In order to successfully form the gender function of gender competence in future teachers, the following conditions must be met.

1. Taking into account the gender affiliation and gender identity of the future teacher when teaching pedagogical subjects.

2. Developing teaching goals, methods, techniques, educational material, its content, individual educational directions of students, and the rhythm of knowledge acquisition that will ensure favorable gender relations. This requires selecting different tasks for each of the boys and girls, and determining the content of the dialogue.

3. Emotional support of communication processes of future teachers

Within the framework of the gender competence of a future teacher, his gender function has a leading, harmonizing character for all other functions, ensuring the personal professional development of the future teacher. All functions formed in a future teacher also ensure the emergence of fundamental changes in his personality. The following components play an important role in determining the gender function of gender competence in students.

The cognitive function of gender competence is implemented through its epistemological component. In this, knowledge about gender stratification and psychophysiological characteristics play a role.

The value functions of gender competence are implemented through its axiological component. This includes laws, regulations, and subjective value relations related to the understanding of cultural differences between learners of different sexes.

The reflexive function of gender competence is implemented through its regulatory component.

The gender component of gender competence is implemented through its synthesizing (generalizing) component. This component is implemented in the context of knowledge about the psychophysiological, socio-cultural, and gender-

specific pedagogical characteristics of the individual, in the context of favorable, effective, and successful gender relations of learners. These indicators are important in preparing future teachers for pedagogical activities related to the socialization of students based on a gender approach.

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